

INTERFACE DESIGN OF 3D WIRE STRUCTURES FOR METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

S. Kaina^{1*}; B. Kieback¹; D. Weck²; A. Bascha³; E. Kieselstein⁴; G. Stephani⁵, O. Andersen⁵

¹ Technische Universität Dresden, Institute of Material Science (IfWW), Dresden

² Technische Universität Dresden, Institute of Lightweight Engineering and Polymer Technology (ILK), Dresden

³ Magnetech GmbH, Neukirch

⁴ KIESELSTEIN Group, Chemnitz

⁵ Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials (IFAM), Dresden

* Corresponding author (steffen.kaina@ifam-dd.fraunhofer.de)

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1 Introduction

Three-dimensional wire structures are a new type of periodic cellular metal. This open cell material can be used as core layer for sandwich applications or for composite manufacturing by infiltration with liquid metals to create novel metal matrix composites (MMC) in order to increase the impact work of the matrix material and to reinforce the matrix in case of fracture. This paper presents results with regard to the manufacturing of a new MMC with a focus on the interface design to create a good material bonding between steel wires and a cast magnesium alloy matrix, especially AZ91 (9 wt% Al; 1 wt% Zn) alloy.

2. Novel MMCs with embedded 3D wire structures

2.1 Three-dimensional wire structures

Cellular metals with truss-type inner structures like pyramidal lattice truss structures [1] or wire-woven bulk kagome (WBK) [2] are special types of periodic cellular metals. They are manufactured by assembling metal wires in a systematic way. A new kind of this group is a 3D wire structure called strucwire® [3]. Strucwire® consists of wire spirals, systematically assembled in three directions of space. The wires are form-closed interconnected at cross points or nodes. The resulting structure shows orthotropic mechanical properties (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Wire spiral, typical wire cross points, and strucwire® 3D wire structure (from left to right).

2.2 Joining and specimen preparation to create a MMC

In order to stiffen the nodes inside the structure and to stabilize the whole structure, a joining step was introduced. To this end, the wire surface is coated with pure metals in a galvanic or chemical deposition process. The so prepared specimens are brazed during a subsequent heat treatment under inert gas atmosphere. The molten soldering metal filled the nodes by exploitation of the capillary force [4]. In order to realise a MMC material with the desired properties, a good material connection between the surface of the steel wires and the Mg alloy has to be obtained. Because of the insolubility of steel in magnesium, a special metallic interlayer material has to be applied. Consequently, a coating material has to be identified which provides good material bonding during the casting process [5]. The final goal was to develop a coating that acts as a stiffening agent for the nodes as well as an intermediate bonding layer in the casting process.

3. Experimental procedure

3.1 Casting experiments – interface design

To analyze the reaction at the interface of different coating materials, an experimental casting setup had to be developed suitable for rapid cooling and short reaction times comparable to the die casting process (see Figure 2). Therefore a simple geometry in form of a steel bar was chosen as specimen instead of the whole wire structure. The steel bars were coated with different metals by a chemical or galvanic coating process. By a calculation of the thermal conduction of this material combination a matching setup was designed. Based on these results, a special specimen holder for the steel bar was constructed. To realize rapid cooling, the steel bar was put at room temperature into the inductively heated magnesium cast. With this setup, a rapid cooling of about 1 second until solidification of the cast can be achieved. Two thermocouples were integrated in the top and the bottom of the die to measure the temperature during the experiment. To determine the influence of the interface reaction during the casting process, several parameters were varied. Next to the coating thickness the influence of the casting temperature was analyzed. Casting temperatures of 620 °C, 640 °C and 660 °C were chosen. A picture of the specimen holder is given in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Sketch of the experimental casting setup.

Fig. 3. Experimental specimen holder.

Optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-Ray (EDX) were carried out to analyze the new phases formed close to the interface.

3.2 High-pressure die casting experiments

Strucwire® samples made from stainless steel (1.4567) and carbon steel (C50) were prepared with coating and brazing as described in chapter 2.1 for casting experiments in a high-pressure die casting machine. AZ91 magnesium alloy was used for the cast matrix. Figure 4 shows a strucwire sample with a cell size of 5 mm and a wire diameter of 0.63 mm. For the casting experiments, structures with only one cell layer were used because of the size limitation of the die. Figure 5 shows a picture of the casting die with an inlaid strucwire® structure before the casting process. A picture of the test samples is given in Figure 6.

Fig. 4. Strucwire® structure with a cell size of 5 mm for the high-pressure die cast experiments; top view (upper picture), side view (lower picture).

Fig. 5. High-pressure casting die with a strucwire® structure inlay before casting.

Fig. 6. High-pressure die casting samples with a strucwire® inlay after casting with deadhead (left) and without (right).

For the casting experiments, wire structures with a copper and chemical nickel coating were used. The coating thickness was about $10\ \mu\text{m}$. The brazing temperatures were about $1100\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for copper and $920\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for the nickel coating. Brazing was carried out in an argon inert gas atmosphere for 5 minutes. For the casting runs two temperatures ($620\ ^\circ\text{C}$ and $660\ ^\circ\text{C}$) were chosen with a constant temperature of the casting die of $250\ ^\circ\text{C}$.

3.3 Testing and characterisation

After the casting experiments a push-out test was carried out on thin specimens machined out of the cylindrical cast pieces to measure the push-out force. This force represents the shear strength of the interface. The “push-out” testing equipment is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: "Push-out" testing equipment to measure the push-out force of the composite specimens.

In addition to the push-out test as a baseline investigation, also pendulum impact tests with wire structure reinforced high pressure die cast magnesium alloy specimens were carried out to measure the weight specific change in impact work. Figure 8 shows a high pressure die cast specimen with wire structure after a pendulum impact test. In Figure 9 the testing device is illustrated.

Fig. 8. High pressure die cast specimen with wire structure after a pendulum impact test.

Fig. 9. Testing device for the pendulum impact test.

4 Results

4.1 Results of the baseline investigations of the interface design

To analyze the interface reaction at the boundary between the steel and the magnesium alloy, new samples were taken from the middle of the cast parts for optical and electron microscopy analysis. Examples are given in order to illustrate the interconnection of the coating and the matrix during the cast process to create a good interface. Figure 10 shows an electron microscopic picture of a copper coated steel bar after reaction with the magnesium cast at a casting temperature of 620 °C. The copper coating had a thickness of about 8 μm . After the experiment no more copper could be found at the interlayer, which leads to the conclusion that all copper was dissolved in the matrix or reacted to new phases after solidification.

Fig. 10. SEM picture of a copper coated steel bar at the interface after the cast experiment at 620 °C.

The distribution of Mg, Al and Cu at the interface of this specimen is given in Figure 11. The high concentration of aluminum and copper in form of a thin layer along the interface indicates a reaction between the copper of the coating and the aluminum of the magnesium-alloy cast. Because of this reaction and the resulting Cu-Al phases a material bond between the two metallic surfaces could be realized.

Fig. 11. EDX-Mapping; Element distribution of Mg, Al, Cu at the interface of a copper coated steel bar after the casting experiment at 620 °C.

Another example of a successful material bond is shown in Figures 12 and 13. In this case a nickel coated steel bar was used. The galvanic nickel coating had a thickness of about 10 µm. The casting

experiment was carried out with a melt temperature of 660 °C. Figure 12 shows an electron microscopic picture of the interface of this specimen after the cast experiment. The reaction of the nickel coating and the cast is indicated by a broad reaction zone. This reaction zone consists of a high amount of nickel and aluminum with newly formed phases and ensures a good interlayer. The element distribution of this sample is given as an EDX-mapping in Figure 13.

Fig. 12. SEM picture of a nickel coated steel bar at the interface after the cast experiment at 660 °C.

Fig. 13. EDX-Mapping; Element distribution of Mg, Al, Cu at the interface of a nickel coated steel bar after the cast experiment at 660°C.

In order to characterize the quality of the interface bonding of the different specimens, the interface shear strength was determined. To this end, the

push-out force of thin specimens machined out of the cylindrical cast pieces was measured. The diagram in Figure 14 shows the different calculated shear stresses of uncoated or only sandblasted steel substrates in comparison to substrates/specimens with a metallic copper, nickel, or chemical nickel coating. Every value is an arithmetic mean of 5 samples. The red bar in the diagram illustrates the standard deviation. The nickel coated specimen reaches the highest shear strength at a casting temperature of 660 °C, which is more than three times higher than a non coated sample. Copper coated samples achieve nearly the same high shear strength at all tested casting temperatures. Furthermore, there is a trend of higher shear strength with increasing casting temperature because of a higher diffusion activity in the melt. In this diagram only three different coatings with also different thicknesses are compared. The whole experiment series shows that the thickness of the coating have only a minor influence on the shear strength, especially for a coating thickness of more than 5-10 µm. The influence of coatings with less than 5 µm thickness is part of current investigations which are not presented in this paper.

Fig. 14. Interlayer shear strength of thin disc specimens in comparison to the coating material and the casting temperature (red bar denotes the standard deviation).

4.2 Results of the high-pressure die casting experiments

This part presents first results of the high-pressure die casting experiments. After the casting experiments, a pendulum impact test was carried out on these composite structures. In Table 1 the reinforcement factors of the specimens are given.

The factor represents the increase of impact energy in relation to the unreinforced cast matrix. For the pure AZ91 matrix a relatively high porosity of about 6-8 % was measured.

Table 1. Weight specific reinforcement factors of magnesium die cast samples with strucwire inlays measured by pendulum impact test

sample	casting temperature [°C]	reinforcement factor
uncoated	620	1,3
uncoated	660	1,3
Copper coated	620	1,3
Copper coated	660	1,4
Nickel coated	620	1,2
Nickel coated	660	1,5

Fore this test run, a maximum reinforcement of 50 % could be measured for a nickel coated specimen. For uncoated samples, an increase of only of 20 % was detected. This leads to the assumption that the proposed interface connection did not form during the casting process. Figures 15 and 16 illustrate that the assumption was correct and that there was no formation of a distinct material bond after the casting process.

Fig. 15. Polished sample of a copper coated wire structure after high-pressure die casting at 660 °C.

Fig. 16. Polished sample of a chemical nickel coated wire structure after high-pressure die casting at 660 °C.

SEM analyses show that there is a very thin bonding zone of only a few micrometers at the interlayer because of the very low diffusion time of a fraction of a second during the process. To build up a thicker interlayer, a tempering process step at a temperature of 450 °C in argon inert gas atmosphere was performed after the casting process. After the heat treatment, a very thick boundary interlayer formed for both coated samples as shown in Figures 17 and 18. This approach gives the opportunity to create a good material connection.

Fig. 17. Polished sample of a copper coated wire structure after high pressure die casting at 660 °C and a subsequent heat treatment in a argon atmosphere at 450 °C for 60 min.

Fig. 18. Polished sample of a chemical nickel coated wire structure after high-pressure die casting at 660°C and a subsequent heat treatment in argon atmosphere at 450 °C for 60 min.

5 Conclusions

First casting samples show higher impact energy absorption in comparison to an unreinforced matrix of about 50 % even without a good material connection. It was thus shown that the weight specific impact work and fracture toughness of magnesium alloy die cast parts can be significantly improved by creating a new kind of MMC which utilizes 3D wire structures as reinforcement. It was

further shown that the quality of the interface between matrix and reinforcement has a strong influence on the behaviour of the MMC.

Due to a plated metallic coating on the wire/substrate surface a reaction zone could be formed which acts as a boundary layer between the two metallic composite partners to create a new MMC material. First test runs with such wire structures in a high pressure die casting process could not fulfill all expectations for a good interlayer after the casting process. However, it was shown that a subsequent tempering step could be added to create a distinct boundary interlayer. Up to now, no samples with such post treatment could be tested in the pendulum test, however, there is a high probability that the impact work and the energy absorption of the composite structure will be higher than without the additional tempering step. Optimizing the tempering step will also be part of future work.

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